

The need for speed: accelerating cardiac magnetic resonance exams and beyond

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Non-invasive imaging technologies have improved our understanding of human health and disease. Recently, advances in imaging speed, coupled with faster imaging reconstruction, processing and analysis methodologies, have improved accuracy and efficiency, subject comfort, and scan tolerance, facilitated dynamic studies across various fields of research and clinical practice and enabled real-time monitoring and quantitative analyses. Our research has focused on the development of accelerated workflows, including artificial intelligence (AI)-based approaches, particularly for cardiac magnetic resonance imaging (CMR) and 3D optical imaging.

Cardiac Magnetic Resonance Imaging

CMR enables extraction of cardiac function, coronary anatomy, viability, myocardial perfusion, and other measures, in a single imaging session.¹ However, there are still some limitations: it is a relatively slow technique compared to, for example, X-ray computer tomography, and conventionally collects stacks of 2D slices because 3D isotropic high-resolution scans are prohibitively long for clinical practice; 2) exam requires multiple breath-holds which can be challenging for very ill patients; 3) quantitative analyses can be complex and time-consuming.

We have developed XD-ORCCA,² a highly efficient respiratory motion-resolved acquisition and reconstruction frameworks to enable free-breathing 3D whole-heart high isotropic spatial resolution imaging: 1) non-contrast enhanced coronary CMR angiography (CMRA) for assessing coronary artery health, 2) simultaneous non-contrast enhanced CMRA and black-blood CMR for coronary lumen and thrombus visualisation and 3) simultaneous contrast-enhanced CMRA and black-blood late gadolinium enhancement (LGE) for accurate detection of infarct location, size and transmural extent and identification of coronary stenosis.³ These methods combine compressed sensing (to reconstruct images from accelerated/undersampled scans) with respiratory motion correction to achieve clinically feasible and predictable scan times (~7 min, instead of > 40 min [unpredictable due to respiratory motion]).²⁻⁵

Standard myocardial perfusion CMR (pCMR) enables the visualisation of myocardial blood flow.¹ However, it is challenged by low spatial resolution, incomplete cardiac coverage and long breath-holds. Moreover, images are predominantly assessed qualitatively through visual analysis, which is subjective and dependent on expertise. We have developed FOSTERS, an automated in-line pipeline that enables free-breathing and high-resolution pCMR and accurate myocardial blood flow quantification (Fig. 1).^{6,7} This method combines motion correction with a low-rank and sparsity constrained reconstruction to obtain high-quality quantitative images. Then, to speed up reconstructions, a self-supervised deep learning pCMR method called SECRET was proposed to reconstruct the dynamic pCMR times series from undersampled data without requiring fully sampled (reference) data, which is not available in pCMR.⁸⁻¹⁰ Recently, we proposed DIREQT, a model-based reconstruction method to directly estimate quantitative perfusion maps and achieve extremely high acceleration rates, enabling improved resolution and coverage.

AI-based methods were also proposed to speed up and automate complex and time-consuming tasks and reduce the dependence on the experience and training of the operator, such as automated view-planning (DeepCardioPlanner),¹¹ segmentation (SEGANet, Fig. 2),¹² analysis and classification (Clinic-NET+).^{13,14}

3D optical imaging

Compressed sensing and low-rank matrix completion methods have been used to accelerate 3D optical imaging modalities, such as fluorescence molecular tomography, optical projection tomography (OPT) and lightsheet microscopy (LSFM).^{15,16} Accelerated OPT enabled the first longitudinal zebrafish study to quantify tumour angiogenesis and evaluate efficacy of a therapeutic drug.^{16,17} Recently, we proposed a deep learning-based method, enabling 100x faster OPT reconstructions with better image quality.¹⁸ High temporal resolution LSFM imaging for studying physiological processes at the millisecond scale have also been facilitated via scan acceleration techniques. Moreover, we are optimising rapid tissue clearing protocols for marine organisms for high-quality OPT and LSFM imaging.

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Fig. 1 pCMR images showing the passage of contrast agent through the right (RV) and left ventricles (LV) and myocardium. (bottom) FOSTERS enables high-resolution accelerated pCMR scans where patients breathe freely and provides (motion-corrected) myocardial blood flow (MBF) maps with higher diagnostic quality than (top) standard low-resolution pCMR under breath-hold, which is prone to dark-rim (false positives) and motion artefacts that occur, even for this very cooperative patient, at the start/end of a long breath-hold.³

Fig. 2 (left) SEGANet enables a fully automatic segmentation of the left atrium (LA) from short axis dynamic (CINE) Magnetic Resonance Images (MRI) acquired with full cardiac coverage. It also provides reliable automatic estimates of clinical biomarkers such as left atrial volumes and ejection fraction (EF). (right) LA volume throughout the cardiac cycle for two representative subjects: an atrial fibrillation (AF) patient and a healthy subject. LA EF is higher for healthy subjects than AF patients. ¹²

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